

Modified Best Proximity Point Theorem for Cyclic Reich Type Contraction in Metric-Like Spaces

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Abstract

In this paper we introduce the notion of a modified best proximity point and obtain a fixed point theorem for cyclic Reich type contraction in metric-like spaces. An example is given to illustrate the main result.

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1 Introduction and Preliminaries

Theorem 1.1. [1] *Let A and B be nonempty closed subsets of a complete metric space (X, d) , and let $T : A \cup B \mapsto A \cup B$ be such that*

$$T(A) \subset B \text{ and } T(B) \subset A$$

Assume that for all $x \in A$ and $y \in B$,

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq \alpha d(x, y)$$

where $\alpha \in (0, 1)$. Then T has a unique fixed point $u \in A \cap B$

Definition 1.2. [2] *Let A and B be nonempty closed subsets of a complete metric space (X, d) , and let $T : A \cup B \mapsto A \cup B$ be such that*

$$T(A) \subset B \text{ and } T(B) \subset A$$

then T is called cyclic.

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Theorem 1.3. [3] Let A and B be nonempty closed and convex subsets of a complete metric space (X, d) , and let $T : A \cup B \mapsto A \cup B$ be cyclic. Assume that for all $x \in A$ and $y \in B$

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq \alpha d(x, y) + (1 - \alpha)d(A, B)$$

where $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and $d(A, B) = \inf\{d(x, y) : x \in A, y \in B\}$. For $x_0 \in A$, define $x_{n+1} = Tx_n$ for each $n \geq 0$. Then there exists a unique $x \in A$ such that $x_{2n} \rightarrow x$ and

$$d(x, Tx) = d(A, B)$$

Definition 1.4. [2] Let X be a nonempty set. A function $\sigma : X \times X \mapsto \mathbb{R}^+$ is said to be a b -metric-like (or a dislocated b -metric) on X if for any $x, y, z \in X$, the following conditions hold:

- (a) $\sigma(x, y) = 0 \implies x = y$
- (b) $\sigma(x, y) = \sigma(y, x)$
- (c) $\sigma(x, z) \leq \sigma(x, y) + \sigma(y, z)$

The pair (X, σ) is then called a metric-like space.

Definition 1.5. [2] Let (X, σ) be a metric-like space.

- (a) A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X converges to $x \in X$ if and only if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sigma(x_n, x) = \sigma(x, x)$
- (b) $\{x_n\}$ is Cauchy in (X, σ) if and only if $\lim_{n, m \rightarrow \infty} \sigma(x_n, x_m)$ exists and is finite
- (c) (X, σ) is complete if and only if each Cauchy sequence in X is convergent

Definition 1.6. [2] Let (X, σ) be a metric-like space. Consider A and B two nonempty subsets of X . An element $a \in X$ is said to be a best proximity point of $T : A \mapsto B$ if

$$\sigma(a, Ta) = \sigma(A, B)$$

where $\sigma(A, B) = \inf\{\sigma(a, b) : a \in A, b \in B\}$

Definition 1.7. [2] Let (X, σ) be a metric-like space, and A and B be nonempty subsets of X . Take the cyclic mapping $T : A \cup B \mapsto A \cup B$

- (a) T is said to be a cyclic Kannan type contraction if

$$\sigma(Tx, Ty) \leq k(\sigma(x, Tx) + \sigma(y, Ty)) + (1 - 2k)\sigma(A, B)$$

for all $x \in A$ and $y \in B$, where $k \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$

- (b) T is said to be a cyclic Chatterjee type contraction if

$$\sigma(Tx, Ty) \leq k(\sigma(Tx, y) + \sigma(Ty, x)) + (1 - 4k)\sigma(A, B)$$

for all $x \in A$ and $y \in B$, where $k \in (0, \frac{1}{4})$

- (c) T is said to be a cyclic Ciric type contraction if

$$\sigma(Tx, Ty) \leq k \max\{\sigma(x, y), \sigma(Tx, x), \sigma(Ty, y)\} + (1 - k)\sigma(A, B)$$

for all $x \in A$ and $y \in B$, where $k \in (0, 1)$

Theorem 1.8. [2] Let A and B be nonempty closed subsets of a complete metric-like space (X, σ) . Let $T : A \cup B \mapsto A \cup B$ be a cyclic Kannan type mapping. For $x_0 \in A \cup B$, define $x_{n+1} = Tx_n$ for each $n \geq 0$. Then

$$\sigma(x_n, x_{n+1}) \rightarrow \sigma(A, B) \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

We have

- (a) If $x_0 \in A$ and $\{x_{2n}\}$ has a subsequence $\{x_{2n_i}\}$ converging to $u \in A$ with $\sigma(u, u) = 0$, then $u \in A$ is a best proximity point of T , that is,

$$\sigma(u, Tu) = \sigma(A, B)$$

- (b) If $x_0 \in B$ and $\{x_{2n-1}\}$ has a subsequence $\{x_{2n_i-1}\}$ converging to $v \in B$ with $\sigma(v, v) = 0$, then $v \in B$ is a best proximity point of T , that is,

$$\sigma(v, Tv) = \sigma(A, B)$$

Theorem 1.9. [2] Let A and B be nonempty closed subsets of a complete metric-like space (X, σ) . Let $T : A \cup B \mapsto A \cup B$ be a cyclic Chatterjee type mapping. For $x_0 \in A \cup B$, define $x_{n+1} = Tx_n$ for each $n \geq 0$. Then

$$\sigma(x_n, x_{n+1}) \rightarrow \sigma(A, B) \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

We have

- (a) If $x_0 \in A$ and $\{x_{2n}\}$ has a subsequence $\{x_{2n_i}\}$ converging to $u \in A$ with $\sigma(u, u) = 0$, then $u \in A$ is a best proximity point of T , that is,

$$\sigma(u, Tu) = \sigma(A, B)$$

- (b) If $x_0 \in B$ and $\{x_{2n-1}\}$ has a subsequence $\{x_{2n_i-1}\}$ converging to $v \in B$ with $\sigma(v, v) = 0$, then $v \in B$ is a best proximity point of T , that is,

$$\sigma(v, Tv) = \sigma(A, B)$$

Theorem 1.10. [2] Let A and B be nonempty closed subsets of a complete metric-like space (X, σ) . Let $T : A \cup B \mapsto A \cup B$ be a cyclic Ćirić type mapping. For $x_0 \in A \cup B$, define $x_{n+1} = Tx_n$ for each $n \geq 0$. Then

$$\sigma(x_n, x_{n+1}) \rightarrow \sigma(A, B) \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

We have

- (a) If $x_0 \in A$ and $\{x_{2n}\}$ has a subsequence $\{x_{2n_i}\}$ converging to $u \in A$ with $\sigma(u, u) = 0$, then $u \in A$ is a best proximity point of T , that is,

$$\sigma(u, Tu) = \sigma(A, B)$$

- (b) If $x_0 \in B$ and $\{x_{2n-1}\}$ has a subsequence $\{x_{2n_i-1}\}$ converging to $v \in B$ with $\sigma(v, v) = 0$, then $v \in B$ is a best proximity point of T , that is,

$$\sigma(v, Tv) = \sigma(A, B)$$

Theorem 1.11. [4] Let (X, d) be a complete metric space and let $f : X \mapsto X$ be a Reich type single-valued (a, b, c) -contraction, that is, there exists nonnegative numbers a, b, c with $a + b + c < 1$ such that

$$d(f(x), f(y)) \leq ad(x, y) + bd(x, f(x)) + cd(y, f(y))$$

for each $x, y \in X$. Then T has a unique fixed point.

2 Main Result

Definition 2.1. Let (X, σ) be a metric-like space. Consider A and B two nonempty subsets of X . An element $a \in X$ will be called a modified best proximity point of $T : A \mapsto B$ if there exist $k \geq 1$ such that $\sigma(a, Ta) = k\sigma(A, B)$, where $\sigma(A, B) = \inf\{\sigma(a, b) : a \in A, b \in B\}$

Definition 2.2. Let (X, σ) be a metric-like space, and A and B be nonempty subsets of X . Take the cyclic mapping $T : A \cup B \mapsto A \cup B$. T will be called a cyclic Reich type contraction if

$$\sigma(Tx, Ty) \leq k(\sigma(x, Tx) + \sigma(y, Ty) + \sigma(x, y)) + (1 - 3k)\sigma(A, B)$$

for all $x \in A$ and $y \in B$, where $k \in (0, \frac{1}{3})$

Theorem 2.3. Let A and B be nonempty closed subsets of a complete metric-like space (X, σ) . Let $T : A \cup B \mapsto A \cup B$ be a cyclic Reich type mapping. For $x_0 \in A \cup B$, define $x_{n+1} = Tx_n$ for each $n \geq 0$. Then

$$\sigma(x_n, x_{n+1}) \rightarrow \sigma(A, B) \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

We have

- (a) If $x_0 \in A$ and $\{x_{2n}\}$ has a subsequence $\{x_{2n_i}\}$ converging to $u \in A$ with $\sigma(u, u) = 0$, then $u \in A$ is a modified best proximity point of T , that is,

$$\sigma(u, Tu) = 2\sigma(A, B)$$

- (b) If $x_0 \in B$ and $\{x_{2n-1}\}$ has a subsequence $\{x_{2n_i-1}\}$ converging to $v \in B$ with $\sigma(v, v) = 0$, then $v \in B$ is a modified best proximity point of T , that is,

$$\sigma(v, Tv) = 2\sigma(A, B)$$

Proof. Let $x_0 \in A \cup B$. Define $x_{n+1} = Tx_n$ for all $n \geq 0$. Since T is a cyclic Reich type mapping, we have,

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma(x_{n+2}, x_{n+1}) &= \sigma(Tx_{n+1}, Tx_n) \\ &\leq k(\sigma(x_{n+1}, Tx_{n+1}) + \sigma(x_n, Tx_n) + \sigma(x_{n+1}, x_n)) + (1 - 3k)\sigma(A, B) \\ &= k(\sigma(x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}) + \sigma(x_n, x_{n+1}) + \sigma(x_{n+1}, x_n)) + (1 - 3k)\sigma(A, B) \\ &\leq k(\sigma(x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}) + 2\sigma(x_n, x_{n+1})) + (1 - 3k)\sigma(x_{n+1}, x_n) \\ &= k\sigma(x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}) + (1 - k)\sigma(x_n, x_{n+1}) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $\sigma(x_{n+2}, x_{n+1}) \leq \sigma(x_n, x_{n+1})$ for all $n \geq 0$, that is, $\{\sigma(x_{n+1}, x_n)\}$ is nonincreasing and is bounded below, so there exist $t \geq 0$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sigma(x_{n+1}, x_n) = t$. Since

$$\sigma(A, B) \leq \sigma(x_{n+2}, x_{n+1}) \leq k(\sigma(x_{n+2}, x_{n+1}) + 2\sigma(x_n, x_{n+1})) + (1 - 3k)\sigma(A, B)$$

if we take limits in the above inequality as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we deduce that $t = \sigma(A, B)$, that is, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sigma(x_n, x_{n+1}) = \sigma(A, B)$. Now, assume that $x_0 \in A$. Since T is cyclic, then $\{x_{2n}\} \in A$, and $\{x_{2n+1}\} \in B$ for all $n \geq 0$. Now if $\{x_{2n}\}$ has a subsequence $\{x_{2n_i}\}$ converging to $u \in A$ with $\sigma(u, u) = 0$, then

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \sigma(x_{2n_i}, u) = \sigma(u, u) = 0$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma(A, B) &\leq \sigma(u, x_{2n_i}) + \sigma(x_{2n_i}, Tu) \\ &\leq \sigma(u, x_{2n_i}) + \sigma(Tx_{2n_i-1}, Tu) \\ &\leq \sigma(u, x_{2n_i}) + k(\sigma(x_{2n_i-1}, x_{2n_i}) + \sigma(Tu, u) + \sigma(x_{2n_i-1}, u)) + (1 - 3k)\sigma(A, B)\end{aligned}$$

Since $\sigma(x_n, x_{n+1}) \rightarrow \sigma(A, B)$, if we take limits in the above inequality as $i \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain,

$$\sigma(A, B) \leq k(\sigma(A, B) + \sigma(Tu, u)) + (1 - 3k)\sigma(A, B)$$

Thus, $\sigma(u, Tu) = 2\sigma(A, B)$, that is, u is a modified best proximity point of T . The proof of case (b) is similar, so we omit it. \square

Now we have the following to illustrate the above theorem

Example 2.4. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be endowed with the metric-like σ defined by

$$\sigma(x, y) = x + y \text{ for all } x, y \in X$$

Note that (X, σ) is a complete metric-like space. Take $A = \{0\}$ and $B = \{1, 2\}$. We have $\sigma(A, B) = 1$. Choose $T : A \cup B \mapsto A \cup B$ as

$$T0 = 1 \text{ and } T1 = T2 = 0$$

We have $T(A) = \{1\} \subset B$ and $T(B) = \{0\} = A$. Let $k \in (0, \frac{1}{3})$. Let $x \in A$ and $y \in B$, then $x = 0$ and $y \in \{1, 2\}$. In this case we have

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma(Tx, Ty) &= \sigma(1, 0) \\ &= 1 \\ &= 3k + 1 - 3k \\ &\leq k(1 + 2y) + (1 - 3k) \\ &= k(0 + 1 + y + 0 + 0 + y) + (1 - 3k)\sigma(A, B) \\ &= k(\sigma(x, Tx) + \sigma(y, Ty) + \sigma(x, y)) + (1 - 3k)\sigma(A, B)\end{aligned}$$

Thus, T is a cyclic Reich mapping for all $x \in A$ and $y \in B$. Now, choose $x_0 \in A \cup B$ such that $x_{n+1} = Tx_n$ for all $n \geq 0$. If $x_0 \in A$, then $x_{2n} = 0$ and $x_{2n+1} = 1$ for all $n \geq 0$. While, if $x_0 \in B$, then $x_{2n} = 1$ for all $n \geq 1$ and $x_{2n+1} = 0$ for all $n \geq 0$. We conclude that for all $n \geq 1$,

$$\sigma(x_n, x_{n+1}) = \sigma(1, 0) = 1 = \sigma(A, B)$$

that is $\sigma(x_n, x_{n+1}) \rightarrow \sigma(A, B)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Now, in the case $x_0 \in A$ we have $x_{2n} = 0$, so that it has a subsequence $\{x_{2n_i}\}$ converging to $u = 0 \in A$. Here $\sigma(u, u) = 0$ and $u = 0$ is a modified best proximity of T .

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